

Original Research

Nanoparticles in Photocatalysis: Innovations Driving Sustainable Dye Degradation in Wastewater Treatment

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Graphical Abstract

Abstract

The rapid industrialization and growing reliance on synthetic dyes have caused a notable rise in water contamination, posing severe threats to aquatic habitats as well as human health. Photocatalysis, an advanced oxidation process, has emerged as a promising and eco-friendly strategy for the treatment of wastewater, particularly for degradation due to persistent dye pollutants. Recent advancements in nanotechnology have further enhanced the efficiency of photocatalytic processes, with nanoparticles playing a pivotal role because of their huge surface area, distinct physicochemical characteristics, and exceptional catalytic activity. This review comprehensively explores the innovations in photocatalysis driven by nanoparticles, with an emphasis on using nanoparticles that have been greenly produced. These nanoparticles, derived from plant extracts or other environmentally benign methods, offer a sustainable substitute for traditional synthesis methods by lowering the environmental effect and using less hazardous chemicals. The paper delves into the synthesis routes, characterization techniques, and mechanistic insights into

dye degradation using green nanoparticles as photocatalysts. This review provides a useful tool for practitioners and scholars looking to develop innovative and eco-friendly strategies for dye degradation and water purification.

Keywords: Photocatalysis, Advanced Oxidation Processes, Green Synthesis, Nanoparticles, Biological Synthesis

Introduction

Environmental pollution poses a significant threat to public health, as it serves as a fundamental cause of numerous diseases globally [1]. Water is one of the most essential resources for human survival on the planet [2]. Currently, access to clean water is one of the significant challenges facing society, largely due to the presence of organic dyes that color substrates such as textiles materials, paper, leather, and plastics [3]. It is estimated that around 10-15% of the total dyes produced are released into the environment, primarily through wastewater [4]. Contamination of water by these coloring agents poses a serious threat to life, adversely affecting the surrounding environment, aquatic ecosystems, and especially human health [5].

Dyes can be eliminated from wastewater using various conventional i.e. chemical and physical methods, which includes adsorption [6], coagulation [7], flocculation [8], oxidation [9] and electro chemicals methods [10]. These conventional treatment methods have proven ineffective in managing wastewater containing synthetic dyes and are limited in their practical application due to factors such as cost [11], feasibility [12], efficiency [13], reliability, sludge production, practicality, environmental impact, operational complexity, pre-treatment needs, and the generation of toxic byproducts [14]. The degradation of most dye molecules results in the formation of non-colored dye fragments [15], effectively decolorizing the effluent and meeting the decolorization requirements [16]. However, these non-colored fragments, such as aromatic amines, can be even more toxic than the original dye [17], leading to challenges in solid waste disposal [18]. Dyes encompass a wide range of chemical structures, primarily derived from substituted aromatic and heterocyclic groups, such aromatic amine ($C_6H_5-NH_2$), which is believed to be a suspected carcinogen, phenyl ($C_6H_5-CH_2$) and naphthyl (NO_2-OH), the sole shared trait among them is their capacity to absorb light in the visible range [19]. In this context, semiconductor photocatalysis has garnered significant attention due to its advantages over traditional methods, particularly its efficiency in the photodegradation of organic compounds into simple, non-toxic byproducts such as CO_2 and H_2O [20]. In the photocatalytic process, semiconducting materials or nanoparticles absorb photons with energy equal to or greater than the energy gap, resulting in the generation of positive holes and electrons [21]. The positive holes can interact with water molecules to produce hydroxyl radicals ($\bullet OH$) [22]. Meanwhile, the electrons are captured by O_2 molecules, leading to the formation of reactive superoxide radicals. ($\bullet O_2^-$) formed [23]. Both $\bullet OH$ and $\bullet O_2^-$ radicals are very reactive and lead to the degradation of organic dyes. [24].

Nanoparticles are drawing the attention of many researchers as adsorbents in photocatalysis due to their ease of synthesis [25], manipulated [26], and possess unique characteristics, including their extremely small size and high surface area to volume ratio [27], which leads to both chemical and physical differences in their properties relative to bulk materials with the same chemical composition [27]. Consequently, the design and fabrication of materials with innovative applications can be accomplished by manipulating their shape and size at the nanometer scale [28]. Various methods are employed to fabricate nanoparticles, including solvothermal techniques [29], precipitation-calcination [30], chemical precipitation [31], microwave-assisted hydrothermal [32], and thermal decomposition methods [33]. These methods involve ample reactants and starting materials [34], draggy procedures [35], and complex apparatus [27], high cytotoxicity [36], low productivity [37], and are not ecofriendly [38].

To address the adverse effects of these toxic agents, researchers are now incorporating the principles of green chemistry by utilizing environmentally friendly solvents and methods in the synthesis of nanoparticles [39]. However, the use of plant extracts is a much simpler process that facilitates the bulk production of nanoparticles, as well as the incorporation of various phytochemicals such as phenols [40], flavonoids, terpenoids found in plant extracts serve as reducing and stabilizing agents in the synthesis of nanoparticles [41].

This review paper seeks to offer a thorough overview of the role of nanoparticles in photocatalysis, emphasizing the latest advancements that promote sustainable dye degradation in wastewater treatment. We will examine the properties, characteristics, and synthesis of nanoparticles, particularly through green approaches, as well as their mechanisms of action in photocatalytic processes to transform wastewater treatment and enhance environmental sustainability. Through this exploration, we aim to highlight the essential role of integrating nanotechnology into photocatalytic systems as a practical solution for tackling the urgent problem of water pollution.

2. Dyes

Textile corporations generate fibers into thread, which is eventually transformed into cloth [42]. They color the fabric in a variety of methods [43]. For instance, dyeing is the procedure of applying dyes uniformly over a textile material [44]. The technique used to apply coloured designated section of the cloth is called printing [45]. The fibers of textiles can be dyed or retained uncolored by bleaching; other refining methods are crosslinking, brittleness and the hydrophobic [46].

2.1. Classification of Dyes

Based on where they come from, dyes are separated into two groups [47]. Since the dawn of time, people have utilized natural colors, which are mainly sourced from plant life, whereas artificial colors are made intentionally using chemicals [48]. Based on the type of fiber they make, there are a total of three different kinds of artificial dyes. These include dyes for synthetic, the protein, and fibers made from cellulose [43]. Fig.1. illustrated classification of Dyes.

Fig.1. Classification of Dyes

2.2. Harmful Effects of Dye

Pollution from the dyeing, printing, as well as finishing industries, has grown to be a significant issue [49].

2.2.1. Air Contamination

Most wet processing techniques result in emissions of gases [50]. Gaseous air was recently determined to be the second most major pollution source in the printing and dyeing industries [51]. Air is polluted by several gases, including CO₂, nitrogen oxides, sulfur dioxide, and others with high concentration. The water treatment plants for fabric preparation, coloring, resin wrapping up, and printing are all important sources of contaminants in the textile industry [52].

2.2.2. Soil Pollution

Due to the overuse of dyes, textile printing and dyeing produce enormous amounts of wastewater at different stages of the textile production process [53]. Soil pollution may result from underground leakage and inadvertent spills of harmful substances from textile manufacturers [54]. In addition, for long time irrigation polluted water containing harmful effluents, are one of the primary causes of dye component transfer to the soil [55]. Dye waste contains inorganic and organic contaminants that are harmful to the soil because they are allergenic [56], mutagenic, and carcinogenic. Contamination of soil dyes has a severe impact on agricultural yield [57].

2.2.3. Water Contamination

In the textile business, the wet treatment of textiles uses a lot of chemicals and water [53]. These industries discharge raw wastewater into local waterways after processing [58]. During the passage of effluents, hazardous substances infiltrate and percolate into the soils, causing damage to soil, subsurface water, pools, and vegetation [59]. Toxic effluents from various sectors create deleterious influence on water, the fertility of the soil [60]. A lot of water is used in the textile sector, from cleaning raw wool or creating synthetic fibers to garment manufacturing [61]. The dyes in textiles interfere with the photosynthesis process [62], stunt the growth of plants, get into the food chain, lead to bioaccumulation, and can enhance oxygen consumption, mutagenicity, carcinogenicity, and toxic consequences [63].

2.2.4. Dyes Harmful Effects on Different Populations

Both mammalian and aquatic species can be poisoned by dyes [64]. In natural ecosystems, dyes cannot be disposable and result in significant pollution [65]. Toxins found in textile industry wastewater affect animal habitats and survival [66]. The availability and permanence of contaminants in food, water and physiochemical properties all influence toxicant bioaccumulation [67].

2.2.5. Impact on the Population of Microbial

Dye gathers in rocks as well as soil or finds its way into open waterways, where it degrades the ecosystem and impacts microbial populations [68]. Where dyes persist pollutants in the environment and cross entire food chains, resulting in bio magnification and greater concentrations of pollutants in comparison to their respective prey [69].

2.2.6. Impact of Dyes on Fish

Changes in the water's composition causes a variety of various physiologic and biochemical problems in fish [70]. Dyes frequently come into touch with fish during gill breathing [71]. Pollutants damage fish organs biochemically when they get there [72].

2.2.7. Impact on Farming

Farm lands can become contaminated by a variety of industrial effluents, wreaking havoc on soil quality and the growth of plants [73]. Dissolved chemicals in industrial effluents can modify the physical conditions in soil as well as water, affecting plant development and yield [74]. The dyes get released into waterways, which are widely used for irrigation in agriculture [75]. Furthermore, the high particle content of effluent limits the amount of oxygen that is dissolved in the water, restricting seed growth and development. Dissolved particles in wastewater likely inhibit seed germination [76].

2.2.8. Effect on the Health of Humans

The usage of polluted groundwater causes serious health problems and, in certain instances, death in humans [77]. Because reactive dyes are mutagenic, carcinogenic, and not biodegradable, they are a significant source of concern in textile effluents [78], so cannot be treated using standard treatment techniques [4]. Moreover, wastewater derived pigments enter the bodies of aquatic creatures, travel up food chains, and eventually end up in people, where they can lead to a variety of physiological problems like fever, cramps, kidney damage, and hypertension [79].

2.2.9. Cancer

Cancer is one of the world's major causes of death [80]. A variety of carcinogenic compounds found in dyestuff can change cell signaling pathways and cause genetic changes [81]. Many dyes were used by textile manufacturing, such as dyes made from azo compounds, have been linked to cancer [82]. Azo dyes are employed to color textiles and come into direct touch with the skin [83]. Depending on the circumstances, there is a high likelihood of skin absorption [84].

2.2.10. Effect on Liver

Because food colorings tend to increase oxidative stress and decrease antioxidant enzyme activity, they have been connected to liver damage [85]. Damage to the antioxidant defense system and increased levels of oxidative stress that come from it have been linked to a number of diseases [86]. Humans are routinely exposed to a variety of food colors as well as chemical solvents used in various industrial processes that are linked to hepatotoxicity [87].

2.2.11. Impact on Central Nervous System

Solutions that are chlorinated are employed in the textile industry to dissolve various chemicals during the manufacturing and washing of clothes [88]. Furthermore, chlorobenzene is employed in the creation of textile colors dyes, insecticides [89]. The effects of chlorobenzene exposure effects on the liver as well as a nervous system, were the most common [90].

3. Conventional Methods of Dye Removal

Water pollution control is a major concern for scientists in terms of protecting and conserving natural water resources. In the literature, many physical, chemical, and biological strategies for dye removal, such as adsorption, have been reported [91], Biosorption, the ozonation coagulation, reversible osmosis, ultrafiltration, nanofiltration, electrolytic degradation, biodegradation, and hybrid biological treatment are all examples of biological treatments [92]. Conventional Methods of Dye Removal are given in fig.2.

Fig.2. Conventional Methods of Dye Removal

3.1. Disadvantage of Conventional Methods for Dye Removal

Every traditional treatment technique has limitations and disadvantages that restrict its practical use, including cost, efficacy, feasibility [93], dependability, practicality, sludge manufacturing, environmental impact, pre-treatment requirements, operation complexity, and the generation of hazardous byproducts [10]. Coagulation, for example, are non-destructive processes that result in the change of colors from one phase of water to another and the generation of secondary pollution, limiting the efficiency of decontamination [94]. The limited efficiency and high cost of activated carbon in adsorption are its disadvantages. Even developing nations and small manufacturing facilities cannot afford it on a broad basis [95]. The disadvantage of filtering methods such as microfiltration, ultrafiltration, and nanofiltration is that pores become clogged, rendering the operation ineffective [96]. To dispose of hazardous substances, a chemical and filter procedure produces heavy sludge, which increases the number of downstream processing steps [97]. Because of electrode changes and electricity consumption, the electrolysis method is not cost-effective [98]. The primary disadvantages of ozonation include the production of hazardous byproducts [99], high energy costs [100], and low ozone solubility in water [101]. Likewise, during biodegradation, bacteria aerobically partially oxidize pigment molecules to create volatile carcinogens [102]. Dye biodegradation effluents may be dangerous, and if the breakdown products come into contact with oxygen, reverse colorization may happen [103]. One of the main uses of semiconductor photocatalysis as is the cleaning of water and wastewater [104].

4. Nanoparticles

The study of material properties that occur at the nanoscale are called nanotechnology, and it devotes specifically to the particular, size-dependent features of the solid-body substances [105]. The Latin word nanus, referring to "dwarf" and thus "very small," is the source of the prefix "nano"[106]. Compared to their bulkier cousins, they are more reactive due to their tiny dimensions, huge surface region with abundant dangling bonds, and increased reactivity, they have unique and fascinating features [107]. Because of their special properties, nanomaterials have applications in numerous applications such as agriculture, medicine, water purification, energy storage, and catalysis [108]. Nanomaterials behave significantly differently than larger-scale materials due to two major factors: quantum and impact on surface [109]. These properties give tiny particles additional or distinctive properties in the areas of thermodynamics, mechanical, magnetic as well as catalysis [27].

4.1. Features of Nanoparticles

Chemical as well as physical characteristics are the two major categories for nanoparticle features.

4.1.1. Physical Features

The nanoparticle's visual characteristics, including its color, penetration of light, absorption, and reflection capabilities, as well as its ultraviolet absorption along with reflecting capabilities in the solution or when placed to a surface, are included in its physical attributes [110]. It also includes their mechanical characteristics that are crucial for their intended use like elasticity, rigidity, tensile strength and adaptability [111]. Many contemporary products now include additional qualities like hydrophilic nature, hydrophilic properties, and suspended form. dispersion, and settlement qualities [112]. Thermal conductivity in applications involving renewable energy and electrical conductivity and resistance in magnetic and electrical properties have led to the use of nanoparticles in contemporary electronics [113].

4.1.2. Chemical Features

The functions of nanoparticles are defined by the chemical properties they possess, that involve how they interact with desired outcomes, strength, and susceptibility to various environmental factors, including light, heat, and humidity [114]. Medical and environmental fields can benefit from the use of tiny particles in antimicrobial, antifungal, sanitizing and toxicological properties [115]. The applications for nanoparticles are determined by their destruction, reduction, flammability, anti-corrosive, and oxidizing capabilities [116].

4.2. Classification of Nanoparticles

There are several techniques for classifying nanomaterial given in fig.3.

Fig.3. Classification of NPs

4.2.1. Classification of NPs on the Base of Materials

In general, there are three distinct kinds of nanoparticles: based on carbon, organic in nature, and inorganic.

4.2.1.1. Organic NPs

Organic material or polymer nanoparticles include ferritin, liposomes, dendrimers, and micelles. [117]. Certain nanoparticles, like liposomes and micelles, have a hollowed center and responsive to electromagnetic and the thermal radiation, including light as well as heat [118]. These tiny particles are also disposable and harmless. Their unique characteristics make them an excellent viewpoint for medication delivery [119]. Along with their usual traits, like size, shape, and surface, they also have the capacity to transport drugs, strength, and delivery methods whether adsorbed or entrapped determine the effectiveness and range of utilization [33].

4.2.1.2. Inorganic NPs

Non-carbon based particles are referred to as inorganic nanoparticles. Inorganic nanoparticles are frequently referred to by their composition composed of metal and the metal oxides [120].

4.2.1.3. Metal Based NPs

Based on the metal nanoparticles originate by metals using either harmful or beneficial methods and are manufactured to nanometric sizes [121]. Nanoparticles may be created from almost any metal [122]. Greater surface area related to volume proportions, particle diameters, surface charges, the density, and the variation between amorphous, crystal-like structures, circular and cylinder-like shapes, colors, and responsiveness to various environmental elements like moisture, humidity, heat, and light are just a few of the special features of nanoparticles [123].

4.2.1.4. Metal Oxides Based NPs

Metal oxide-based nanoparticles are produced in order to change the characteristics of the comparable metal-based nanoparticles [124]. In particular, iron NPs rapidly converted to iron oxide at room temperature, thereby increasing their ability to react in comparison to iron NPs [125]. These tiny particles have exceptional qualities when contrasted against the metal counterparts [126].

4.2.1.5. Carbon Based NPs

Carbon nanoparticles referred to as carbon-based NPs [127]. Among these are graphene in appearance fullerenes, a carbon black, the nanotubes made of carbon as well as nanoscale activated carbon [128].

4.2.2. Classification of NPs on the Base of Dimensions

Nanomaterials are substances are described as materials comprising a minimum of one dimension that is nanoscale, or smaller than 100 nm [129]. On the basis of size, nanostructures can be grouped into four groups.

4.2.2.1. Zero-Dimensional Nanomaterials (0-D)

This group nanomaterials has all three dimensions on the nanoscale scale [130]. Quantum dots, fullerenes, are

nanoparticles examples.

4.2.2.2. One-Dimensional Nanomaterials (1-D)

There is only one dimension in this family of materials that is missing at the nanoscale [131]. Nanotubes, nanofibers, nanorods, nanowires, and nano horns are some examples.

4.2.2.3. Two-Dimensional Nanomaterials (2-D)

The materials within this category have two dimensions that extend outside of the nanoscale. Examples include nanosheets and nanolayers [132].

4.2.2.4. Three-Dimensional Nanomaterials (3-D)

There are no dimensions on which substances in this category cannot reach the nanoscale. Bulk powders, arrays of nanowires and nanotubes, and other materials are included in this group of materials [133].

4.3. Synthesis of Nanoparticles

There are several different processes that can be categorized as either bottom-up or the top-down processes that produce nanoparticles [134]. Simplified process example is illustrated in fig. 4.

Fig.4. Synthesis of Nanoparticles

4.3.1. Bottom Up Approach

Atoms, which are clusters, and nanoparticles can all be formed via bottom up or the constructive procedures [135]. For the manufacture of nanoparticles in the bottom up processes such as pyrolysis, spinning, the chemically vapor deposition, sol-gel and biosynthesis [136].

4.3.1.1. Sol-Gel

A uniform solution with particles floating in the form of water is called a sol. A gel is an inert molecule submerged in a liquid. Because sol gel production is so simple to utilize and can produce the majority of nanoparticles, it is an extremely often used bottom up approach. It involves a wet-chemical technique that starts with a chemical solution to create a separate particles structure that is ordered [137].

4.3.1.2. Spinning Approach

The process of spinning to create nanostructures is called spinning disc reactor. It is made up of a rotating disc that is housed in a chamber with physical elements like temperature [138]. Atoms mix due to the speed of spinning, resulting in the process of precipitation collecting, and drying. A variety of functional parameters, including the flow of liquid rate, disc rotation velocity, precursors ratio, feed status, disc appear, and so forth, influence the characteristics of the nanoparticles produced by SDR [139].

4.3.1.3. Chemical Vapor Deposition

Chemical vapor deposition details procedure of spreading a thin coating of reactant gases onto a substrate. A chemical reaction takes place when the combined gases and a substrate that is heated get into contact. The ambient temperature of the surface controls CVD. Nanoparticles produced by CVD are incredibly robust, homogenous, hard, and pure. The extremely dangerous gaseous byproducts and the requirement for specialized machinery are two disadvantages of CVD

[28].

4.3.1.4. Pyrolysis Approach

One method that's very popular in industry for producing vast quantities of nanoparticles is pyrolysis. It requires combustion a starting point with flames. By an extremely small aperture, the product which can be alternatively a liquid or a vapor is injected under high pressure into the furnace and burned. The residues of combustion or resulting gases are classified as air in order to restore the nanoparticles [140].

4.3.1.5. Biosynthesis Approach

The process of biosynthesis is an environmentally friendly and sustainable technique that yields non-toxic, biodegradable nanoparticles [141]. Using bacteria, extracts of plants, fungi biosynthesis produces NPs instead of using traditional chemicals for capping and bioreduction [142]. The biosynthesized nanoparticles' distinct and improved properties qualify them for application in biological domains [143].

4.3.2. Top Down Approach

The destructive or the top down process involves reducing an enormous amount of material to the nanometric-sized fragments [144]. The most popular methods for creating nanoparticles consist of heat breakdown, the sputtering, the laser treatment, mechanically milling, as well as nanolithography [145].

4.3.2.1. Mechanical Milling Process

The use of mechanical milling is the top down approach that's used most often to generate various sorts of nanoparticles [146]. When different parts are ground in an inert atmosphere during synthesis or upon the annealing of tiny particles, mechanical milling is utilized [34].

4.3.2.2. Nanolithography

Nanolithography is the term used to describe the method of producing nanometric size structures with at least one dimension that is within the 1–100 nm range [147]. Optical signals electron-beam, nanoimprint, as well as scanning probe lithography are examples of nanolithographic methods. In overall, lithography is a process that selectively removes material to create the desired form and structure in order to print a shape and pattern on a material that is sensitive to light [148]. The primary advantage of nanolithography is its ability to produce anything from a single, minuscule particle to a collection of particles with the right size and shape. Drawbacks include the additional expenses and requirement for advanced technologies [149].

4.3.2.3. Laser Ablation Process

Creating nanoparticles from different solvents is a common application of Laser Ablation Production in Solution [150]. A plasma plume condenses when a metal immersed in a liquid solution is subjected to a laser beam, producing nanoparticles. LASiS can produce stable nanoparticles without the need for chemicals or stabilization substances in a mixture of biological fluids and water, it is considered a "green" approach [151].

4.3.2.4. Sputtering

The technique of Sputtering involves ejecting particles onto an object's surface when they impact with ions in order to deposit nanoparticles there [152]. The usual characteristic of sputtering is the following processing that results in the coating of a tiny amount of nanoparticles. The substrate type, the temperature of annealing and duration, coating thickness, and other variables all affect the morphology and dimensions of the NPs [153].

4.3.2.5. Thermal Decomposition Process

Endothermic method commonly referred as "thermal decomposition" because heat induces materials which break down all chemical connections inside the material [154]. The exact degree at which a component undergoes thermal breakdown is known as its breakdown temperature. By breaking down a metal at certain the temperature, which causes a chemical response that yields intermediate chemicals, nanoparticles are produced [155].

4.4. Benefits of Nanoparticles

Here is a list of among the many significant uses for nanoparticles in Fig.5.

Fig.5. Applications of Nanoparticles

4.4.1. Sunscreens and the Beauty Products

Usual UV protection sunblock becomes unsustainable [156]. Utilizing nanoparticles in sunscreen, like titanium dioxide, offers a number of benefits [157]. The oxides of titanium have found their way into a number of sunscreens due to their ability to both absorb and reflect UV radiation while remaining translucent to visible light [158].

4.4.2. Electronics and Technology

The expanding use of nanotechnology in the display sector is being facilitated by the demand over the past decade for large-sized, high-brightness displays, such as those found in televisions and computer monitors [159]. Light-emitting diodes in modern screens, for instance, use a nanocrystalline, form cadmium sulfide as well as zinc sulfide [160]. There is an enormous need for smaller, lighter, and higher capacity batteries as a result of the advancement of transportable consumer gadgets, that include notebook computers and cell phones [161]. Batteries divider panels made of nanoparticles work quite well [162]. Batteries divider panels made of nanoparticles work quite well. Its foam-like form allows it to store a lot more energy than standard batteries. Batteries made of metal hydrides and nanocrystalline nickel require less recharge because of their large surface area [163].

4.4.3. Catalysis Process

Because of their enormous area of surface, nanoparticles exhibit greater catalytic activity. These nanoparticles' exceptional surface-to-volume ratio makes them useful catalysts in chemical synthesis [164]. One important use is in automotive combustion engines, where the comparatively large circumference of the nanoparticles reduces the total amount of platinum required, resulting in a significant cost reduction and performance improvement [165].

4.4.4. Medicine and Health Care

The utilization of nanotechnology in the administration of drugs has advanced the area of medicine because of nanotechnology [166]. The medication can be delivered to particular cells using nanoparticles [167]. The total amount of drug consumed and its adverse effects are significantly decreased when the medication is applied in the appropriate area and at the recommended dosage [168]. The adverse effects and expense are decreased using this strategy. With the aid of nanotechnology, tissue that is damaged can be replicated and repaired [169].

4.4.5. Food

The processing, wrapping, preservation, and manufacture of food are all improved by the utilization of nanotechnology [170]. For instance, a nanotechnology coating can inject antimicrobial chemicals directly onto the covered film layer during the food packaging process [171].

4.4.6. Construction and Building Process

Building processes have become safer, faster, and less expensive thanks to nanotechnology. Regular concrete may become more durable and have superior mechanical characteristics whenever nano silica is introduced. Paints have the hydrophobic in nature properties to repel water, they may be employed on metal pipes to protect them against saltwater attacks. The inclusion of nanoparticles in paints increases their ability to perform by leaving them lighter and with better characteristics.

4.4.7. Restoration of the Environment and Renewable Energy

Because of their distinctive chemical and physical characteristics, nanoparticles are a great option for cleaning up the environment and enhancing the efficiency of renewable energy sources [172]. Nanoparticles are widely distributed and have been found to have positive environmental effects [173]. The incorporation of nanoparticles in environmental remediation, frequently referred to as nano remediation, has been an effective method for treating and sanitizing the atmosphere, water, and soil for over ten years.

4.5. Applications of Metal Oxide Nanoparticle

Various catalysts have been developed to improve photocatalysis. These metal oxide nanoparticles oxidize easily to form oxides or hydroxides and are less harmful. The band gap, and which permits reduction as well as oxidation by sensing energy from the light source, is another significant characteristic. Metallic oxides with a reduced band gap typically more effective under visible light, meaning they require less money and time to produce due to the absorption modifications to the red band [174]. These metal oxides have a wide range of morphologies, including nanoparticles, nanospheres, nanofibers, nanotubes, nanoribbons, nanosheets, and so on [175]. Metal oxide nanoparticles with various morphologies have numerous applications in fig.6. These morphologies also affect a photocatalyst's efficiency [176].

Fig.6. Applications of Metal Oxide Nanoparticles

4.6. Greener Synthetic Strategies

The manufacturing of nanomaterials using benign substances in the matrix where they are to be used requires the development of "greener" synthetic strategies, which will decrease or eliminate the use of typically utilized dangerous chemicals, being exposed to them, as well as generation risk [177].

4.6.1. Green Chemistry in Nanomaterial Fabrication

Chemicals, starting materials, compounds are among the chemicals utilized in the production of nanocrystals. These compounds have produced toxic intermediates and products. The notion of green chemistry has been introduced into the chemical sector in an effort to decrease the manufacturing of undesirable goods [178].

The principles of green chemistry are given below in fig.7.

Fig.7. Principles of Green Chemistry

Green synthesizing nanoparticles have the following benefits over physical as well as chemical approaches:

- Because no hazardous chemicals are needed, this approach is clean and safe for the environment [179].
- It also reduces the total expense of the procedure of synthesis because the active natural component acts as a reduction and the capping agent [180].
- This can be employed for producing nanoparticles on an enormous scale [181].
- It saves energy because it does not require external conditions for experimentation like high energy or elevated pressure [182].

4.6.2. Primary Source of Environmentally Friendly MONPs

One environmentally benign method of synthesizing MONPs is through the use of living creatures [183]. In addition to being necessary for food and nutrition, living things are also involved in the procedure of green synthesis [184]. Researchers select plants for the environmentally friendly production in MONPs either because of their abundance of feedstock and chemical arsenal or because many of them have biomass available to them [185]. Plants' responses to stressors and survival agents are influenced by their primary and secondary metabolites, which will position plants as the main bioreactors and providers of molecules for green synthesis [186]. Primary plant components like citric acid and the proteins are retained due to MONPs' outermost covering's endurance and the existence of its metallic equivalent [187].

4.6.3. Fabrication of MONPs using Extract from Plant Leaves

Plant biovariation of compounds provides an abundance of biochemical features and introduces a unique source in manufacturing of NPs [188]. The plant extract from the leaves is rather simple to produce and has a number of metabolites can serve as agents that reduce throughout the nanoparticle manufacturing process [40]. Quality, equilibrium, quantity produced and production rate of nanoparticles are all affected by elements that consist of pH, the environment, contact duration, amount of metal salts, and chemical makeup of the plant leaves fragments [189]. Plants reduce metal ions faster than fungi and bacteria because they require more time to incubate due to the abundance of several phytochemicals soluble in water [190]. Phytochemicals in plant leaf extracts are easily extracted [191]. Because biological reducing agents can be found in varying amounts in various kinds of leaf extracts, makeup has significant impact on the nanoparticle production [192].

Fig.8. Uses of Nanoparticles

4.7. Characterization Techniques

Various approaches have been employed for characterization, including UV-visible spectroscopy, which based on a surface plasmon resonance concept [193]. For determining the crystalline phase is X-ray diffraction (XRD) [194]. FTIR spectroscopy, referred to as the Fourier transform, helps determine which functional groups are present in a material [195]. SEM and EDX were used to characterize nanoparticles based on size, shape, and atomic percentage [196].

Fig.9. Characterization Methods of Synthesized Nanoparticles

5. Photocatalytic Dye Removal

The photocatalytic method involves a heterogeneity photo catalysis, semi-conducting absorption that destroys multiple contaminants, including organic pollutants in the atmosphere when exposed to light [197]. It has various advantages over traditional techniques of treating wastewater from industries [198]. For example, even at room temperature, photocatalyst degrades dye material in a short period [199]. More significantly, no toxic residues are formed because it degrades organic contaminants into non-hazardous by products such as H_2O and CO_2 [200]. The degradation efficiency is also influenced by ideal conditions during the process of photocatalysis reaction [201]. These include the amount of time the dye is exposed to light, the pH of the dye solution, the amount of catalyst needed for effective degradation [202], the distance between the dye and the light source, the method's temperature, and the amount of dye-containing solution

[203].

5.1. Heterogeneous Photocatalysis Process

Wastewater has historically been a major problem due to the fast growing population and increasing industries by the potential for total pollutant mineralization in addition to harmful metal ions [204]. The processes of photocatalysis with heterogeneity are essentially explained free radicals are produced after the semiconductor's capacity to produce charged particles adjusts to light irradiation that include OH^\bullet , in the generation of CO_2 as well as H_2O [205]. As a result, the most appealing aspects of heterogeneous photocatalysis are:

- The contaminants entirely break down into CO_2 along with other inorganic compounds under ambient circumstances [206]. The existence of oxygen, may be produced from the air and sun, is the only prerequisite for the reaction to begin [207].
- The catalyst can be reused, is non-toxic, and is affordable [208]. Furthermore, photocatalysis with heterogeneity is among the most economical and environmentally friendly ways to water and air cleanup [209].

5.2. Heterogeneous Photocatalysis Mechanism

A number of oxidation and reducing activities occur on the surface of the photocatalyst as part of the heterogeneous photocatalysis mechanism [20]. A bandgap, represented by E_{bg} , separates the smallest occupied and greatest unoccupied energy regions of a semiconductor [210]. Electrons from the valence bands on the surface are photoexcited and drawn to CB when photons with photon energy more than or equal to the semiconductors' E_{bg} are exposed to light for femtoseconds [211]. This generates electron-hole pair by leaving an unfilled valence in the band, known as a hole (h^+) [212]. If these particles of energy are trapped on the outermost layer of the semiconductor and a sequence of events known as follows takes place [213].

The photocatalytic degradation can be explained by the following equations which are given below:

Fig.10. Heterogeneous Photocatalysis Mechanism

6. Conclusion and Future Perspective

The field of nanoparticle based photocatalysis for wastewater treatment holds immense potential for achieving sustainable and efficient dye degradation. Green synthesized nanoparticles, leveraging plant extracts, present an opportunity to reduce the environmental footprint associated with conventional nanoparticle production while

enhancing biocompatibility and catalytic efficiency. To close the gap between industrial scale applications and laboratory research, comprehensive life cycle assessments and techno economic analyses must be conducted. In conclusion, advancements in nanoparticle photocatalysis, driven by green synthesis and innovative engineering, are essential in reducing water pollution and helping to a cleaner, more sustainable. Advances in material science and computational modeling can further guide the rational design of nanoparticles with enhanced photocatalytic performance. Machine learning and artificial intelligence tools could optimize synthesis parameters, predict catalytic behavior, and accelerate the discovery of novel materials. Future research should prioritize the creation of environmentally friendly, economical, and scalable synthesis techniques, like applying the concept of green chemistry.

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